

COVAX Maternal Immunization Working Group
Template for the Evaluation of Vaccines for Maternal Immunization

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on behalf of the COVAX MI WG

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

ACIP - CDC Advisory Committee on Immunization Practices
ACOG - American College of Obstetrics and Gynecology
ACT - Access to COVID-19 Tools (ACT) Accelerator
AE – Adverse Event
AEFI – Adverse Event Following Immunization
AESI – Adverse Event of Special Interest
AIDS – Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome
CDC – U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
CIOMS - Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences
CMI – Cell-mediated immunity
COVAX – COVID vaccine arm of the Access to COVID-19 Tools Accelerator
CSL – Biotechnology Company
DART – Developmental and Reproductive Toxicology
DSMB – Data Safety Monitoring Board
EUA/EUL – Emergency Use Authorization (FDA) / Emergency Use Listing (WHO)
FDA - U.S. Food and Drug Administration
GSK – GlaxoSmithKline pharmaceutical company
HIC – High Income Country
ICU – Intensive Care Unit
influenza A/H1N12009pdm – strain of influenza virus
IVAC/JHPIEGO – International Vaccine Access Center of the Johns Hopkins Program for International Education in Gynecology and Obstetrics
LMICs – Low-Middle Income Countries
MI – Maternal Immunization
MIS-A – Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in adults
MIS-C – Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children
mRNA – Messenger RNA
NAM - U.S. National Academy of Medicine
NIH – U.S. National Institutes of Health
PCR – Polymerase chain reaction in DNA testing
PREVENT - Pregnancy Research Ethics for Vaccines, Epidemics, and new Technologies
RSV – Respiratory Syncytial Virus
SARs-CoV-2 – Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2; virus causing COVID-19
Th1 and Th2 – T lymphocyte helper cells types 1 and 2
TPP - Target Product Profiles
VAED – Vaccine-associated enhanced disease
VVM- Vaccine vial monitor
WG – Working Group
WHO - World Health Organization
WS – Work Stream

BACKGROUND

COVID-19 and Pregnant Women

Globally, an estimated 213 million pregnancies occur annually.¹ Pregnant and lactating women make up a significant portion of the first responder and frontline health care global workforce. Among the health care workforce in the United States (U.S.) there are over 300,000 women who are of child-bearing age and/or pregnant at any given time. This proportion is likely higher in low and middle-income countries (LMICs), with higher reproductive rates. Health care related occupations are critical to the pandemic response and have been prioritized for COVID-19 vaccine allocation.² Further, women are often employed in occupations that may be associated with potentially high SARS-CoV-2 exposure risk such as childcare providers, teachers, public-facing and hospitality workers, and caregivers. Guidance for COVID-19 immunization strategies for pregnant and lactating women who rely on employment in these high-risk occupations is therefore urgently needed.

In November 2020, the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) included pregnancy as one of the underlying conditions that put adults at increased risk for severe illness from SARS-CoV-2.³ Pregnant women might be at increased risk for severe COVID-19, possibly related to an adapted immune system and altered respiratory physiology.⁴ When compared with non-pregnant women with COVID-19, pregnant women with COVID-19 had a higher risk of hospitalization, intensive care unit (ICU) admission, mechanical ventilation,^{5,6,7} and, in several studies, a higher risk of death.^{8,9,10} Similar to the general population, severe disease appears to be more common among pregnant women who are older (36-44 years), or who have

underlying medical conditions, such as gestational diabetes or hypertension.^{11,12} As in non-pregnant adults, severe disease risk in pregnancy is also associated with obesity.^{13,14,15}

Data from high income countries (HICs) suggest that adverse birth outcomes, such as preterm delivery, are more common among pregnant women infected with SARS-CoV-2, particularly if they are infected in the third trimester.^{16,17,18} Newborns who test positive for COVID-19 are usually born to mothers who tested positive less than one week prior to delivery.¹⁹ Most are asymptomatic or have mild infection and some may require a short stay in neonatal intensive care. Vertical transmission appears to be rare.^{20,21}

Studies from the US and the United Kingdom report that Black and Hispanic women who are pregnant appear to be disproportionately at risk of severe disease and hospitalization.^{22,23} Little or no pregnancy-specific data is available from LMICs largely due to a lack of data collection infrastructure. Additional data will be needed to inform local decision-making.

COVID-19 Vaccines and Pregnant Women

Vaccines for pregnant women are one of the most important public health measures undertaken globally to reduce the burden of tetanus, pertussis and seasonal influenza in mothers and infants. During previous respiratory pathogen pandemics, such as influenza A/H1N12009pdm, infection in pregnant women has been associated with an increased risk for severe disease and hospitalization, and pregnant women have subsequently been prioritized for immunization.²⁴ Various organizations, including the U.S. National Academy of Medicine (NAM),²⁵ the American College of Obstetrics and Gynecology (ACOG),²⁶ the Pregnancy Research Ethics for Vaccines, Epidemics, and new Technologies (PREVENT) group,²⁷ and the World Health

Organization (WHO),²⁸ support the position that pregnant and lactating women are a priority population that must not be excluded from the COVID-19 vaccine allocation strategy.^{29,30}

The Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences (CIOMS) guidelines encouraged the inclusion of pregnant women in clinical studies in 2002,³¹ followed by the United Nations AIDS/World Health Organization in 2005.³² Most recently, the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) published its support for the inclusion of pregnant women in a draft guidance for the pharmaceutical industry.³³ These organizations understand that the exclusion of pregnant women from clinical trials can lead to a lack of data with which they, their families, and their health care providers can make informed decisions about the potential benefits and risks of medications and vaccines administered during pregnancy. In the 2020 “Development and Licensure of Vaccines to Prevent COVID-19” guidance,³⁴ FDA encourages vaccine sponsors to collect and consider “data that might support inclusion of pregnant women and women of childbearing potential who are not actively avoiding pregnancy in pre-licensure clinical trials” because, the use of “COVID-19 preventive vaccines during pregnancy and in women of childbearing potential will be an important consideration for vaccination programs.”

The COVAX Maternal Immunization Working Group

In April 2020, in response to the COVID-19 pandemic, the Access to COVID-19 Tools (ACT) Accelerator,³⁵ a global collaboration, was launched to facilitate the development, production, and equitable access to COVID-19 tests, treatments, and vaccines. The ACT Accelerator’s SARS-CoV-2 vaccine research, development and manufacturing work stream comprises a Clinical Development and Operations SWAT team to identify tools and support for vaccine developers to facilitate COVID-19 vaccine licensure. Recognizing the importance of

addressing the needs of pregnant and lactating women during the COVID-19 pandemic, the SWAT team established the COVAX Maternal Immunization Working Group (MI WG) in August 2020. The COVAX MI WG, comprises a selected, inclusive group of professionals with expertise in various aspects pertinent to maternal immunization, who represent diverse backgrounds, organizations, geographies, and settings, to broadly contribute to the objectives of the working group.

The overarching goal of the COVAX MI WG is to support the availability of at least one COVID-19 vaccine candidate that is suitable for use in pregnant women. To accomplish this goal, the WG set out to 1) describe approaches for the evaluation of COVID-19 vaccine candidates for use in pregnant women and their infants, from pre-licensure clinical studies to the post-licensure period; 2) create an evaluation framework for COVID-19 vaccine candidates for use in pregnant and lactating women; and 3) describe the necessary data and studies to close the availability and access gap to safe and effective COVID-19 vaccination and prevention strategies for pregnant women.

Approach

In order to cover relevant issues pertaining to the inclusion of pregnant women across the vaccine development pathway ranging from the pre-clinical through the post-approval phase, three work streams addressed key questions related to 1) Vaccine Candidate Mapping, 2) Pre-clinical and Clinical Evaluation, and 3) Vaccine Safety. On an ad hoc basis, work stream leads and members also solicited input from external subject matter experts. Ethics and regulatory advisors served to review and advise across all work stream deliberations and

outputs. During weekly or bi-weekly meetings, work stream representatives shared group findings and identified areas of consensus to refine and address their key questions.

Key questions for the preclinical and clinical evaluation of vaccine candidates for pregnant and lactating women

Key questions for the evaluation of COVID-19 vaccines' potential for use during pregnancy and lactation were developed by the MI WG. The key questions serve as an evaluation framework for all stages of COVID-19 vaccine development across the different vaccine platforms. While the focus of the MI WG was on COVID-19 vaccines, this evaluation framework can be applicable to any vaccine under consideration for evaluation and use in pregnant and lactating women. The key questions have been organized in a table (Table 1) divided in sections focusing on the various intersecting issues that comprise the evaluation of vaccine use in pregnant women, including:

Section A. Key Questions on the Pathogen, the Disease and Pregnancy.

Section B. General Questions on Specific Vaccine Platforms and Characteristics (Based on the Brighton Collaboration BRAVATO vaccine platform modules). When pertinent, data collected through Brighton Collaboration BRAVATO tools should inform the evaluation of candidate vaccines in pregnant and lactating women.

Section C. Key Questions on Development and Planning for All Candidate Vaccines (regardless of construct/platform) for Pregnant and Lactating women.

Section D. Key Questions for Post-Licensure Safety Evaluation of Vaccine Use During Pregnancy

Section E. Summary of Evaluation of Vaccine for Use During Pregnancy and Lactation

Table 1. Key Questions for the Evaluation of Vaccine Candidates for Pregnant and Lactating Women.

Key Questions for the Evaluation of Vaccine Candidates for Pregnant and Lactating Women.
Section A. Key Questions on the Pathogen, Disease, and Pregnancy
A.1 What is known of the pathogen and the disease it causes and their effects during pregnancy
1.1 Are pregnant women at greater risk of infection?
1.2 What is the infection rate in pregnant women compared to non-pregnant women/population?
1.3 What are the clinical disease manifestations of disease in pregnant women?
1.4 Are pregnant women at greater risk of severe disease compared to non-pregnant women/population?
1.5 Is the rate of hospitalization greater in pregnant women compared to non-pregnant women/population?
1.6 Is the rate of intensive care admission greater in pregnant women compared to non-pregnant women/population?
1.7 Is the risk of maternal death during pregnancy greater than in non-pregnant women/population?
1.8 Are there disease effects or complications specific to pregnant women?
1.9 Is there a greater risk of infection in a specific trimester of gestation?
1.10 Is there a greater risk of severe disease during a specific trimester of gestation?
1.11 Is there a greater risk of maternal death in a specific trimester of gestation?
1.12 Are there known maternal factors or underlying medical conditions that increase the risk of infection, severe disease, or death?
1.13 What factors or underlying medical conditions increase the risk of infection, severe disease, or death during pregnancy??
1.14 What are other potential effects of infection and disease in pregnancy?
1.15 Are there available safe and effective specific treatments for pregnant women?
1.16 What is the efficacy of existing therapies in pregnant women?
1.17 Are pregnant women included in clinical trials of treatments and vaccines for this disease?
A.2. Pregnancy and Obstetric outcomes:
2.1 What are the adverse obstetric outcomes associated with maternal infection and disease?
2.2 What is the risk of preterm labor in infected vs. non-infected women?
2.3 What is the risk of preterm delivery in infected vs. non-infected women?
2.4 What is the rate of C-section delivery in infected vs. non-infected women?
2.5 What are the indications for C-section delivery in infected women?
2.6 What is the risk of specific maternal obstetric complications associated with infection and disease during pregnancy, including:
2.6.1 Hypertension disorders, eclampsia, preeclampsia
2.6.2 Gestational diabetes
2.6.3 Antenatal and perinatal bleeding
2.6.4 Chorioamnionitis
2.6.5 Maternal infection and sepsis
2.6.6 Post-abortal and post-partum endometritis
A.3. Is there evidence of Vertical Transmission of the pathogen?:
3.1 Via placenta? Describe evidence

3.2 Via breastmilk? Describe evidence
3.3 Is there evidence of placental infection? 3.3.1 If yes, what are the mechanisms of placental infection?
3.4 Is there evidence of transplacental transfer of immunity?
3.5 Is there evidence of transfer of immunity via breast milk?
A.4. Fetuses:
4.1 Does fetal infection occur?
4.2 What is the risk of fetal infection? 4.2.1 What is the risk of fetal infection by trimester of gestation? 4.2.2 Is there evidence of teratogenicity/congenital malformations from infection?
4.3 What is the risk of teratogenicity?
4.4 Is there a risk of fetal loss?
4.5 Is there a risk of fetal loss by trimester of gestation?
4.6 What is the risk of spontaneous abortion/miscarriage?
4.7 What is the risk of stillbirth?
4.8 What is the risk of intrauterine growth restriction?
4.9 Are there other fetal effects/risks associated with maternal infection with SARs-CoV-2?
A.5 Neonates and Infants:
5.1 What is the risk of prematurity with maternal infection?
5.2 What is the risk of neonatal infection?
5.3 What is the mechanism of transmission of neonatal infection from mother to infant?
5.4 What are the clinical manifestations of neonatal infection?
5.5 What is the risk of severe neonatal disease?
5.6 What is the risk of neonatal death?
5.7 What is the risk of neonatal sepsis, meningitis and other infections?
5.8 What is the risk of infection, disease and death in the first 6 months of life?
5.9 What is the risk of infection, disease and death in the first year of life?
A.6 Post-partum and Lactating Women:
6.1 Are post-partum and lactating women at greater risk of infection?
6.2 What is the infection rate in post-partum and lactating women compared to non-pregnant and non-lactating post-partum women population?
6.3 Are post-partum and lactating women at greater risk of severe disease compared to non-pregnant and non-lactating post-partum women?
6.4 Is the rate of hospitalization greater in post-partum and lactating women compared to non-pregnant and non-lactating women?
6.5 Is the rate of intensive care admission greater in post-partum and lactating women with infection compared to non-pregnant and non-lactating post-partum women?
6.6 Is the risk of maternal death during post-partum period greater than in the non-pregnant population?
6.7 Is the risk of maternal death greater in lactating women than non-lactating women?
6.8 Are there complications specific to post-partum and lactating women?
6.9 Are there available antiviral or other specific therapies for post-partum and lactating women?
6.10 What is the efficacy of available treatments in post-partum and lactating women?
6.11 Are post-partum and lactating women included in clinical trials of treatments and vaccines?

Key Questions for the Evaluation of Vaccine Candidates for Pregnant and Lactating Women
Section B. Questions on Specific Vaccine Platforms and Components
B.1 Vaccine name and Manufacturer
B.2 Vaccine Construct/Platform (use tables in the Appendix for specific non-pregnancy questions)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protein/Subunit³⁶ (Appendix V.A) • Nucleic Acid³⁷ (Appendix V.B) • Viral Vector³⁸ (Appendix V.C) • Live vaccines ³⁹ (Appendix V.D) • Inactivated vaccines ⁴⁰ (Appendix V.E)
B.3 General and pre-clinical toxicology studies on vaccine construct and components
<p>3.1 Are there safety data from animal models (pregnant/non-pregnant) with the vaccine construct/platform or any of the vaccine components?</p> <p>3.1.1 Have Developmental and Reproductive Toxicity Studies (DART) been conducted? Describe studies and what component of the vaccine was evaluated (complete vaccine construct or specific components)</p> <p>3.1.2 If yes, are there any identified developmental or reproductive toxicities? If yes, describe.</p> <p>3.1.3 Are there any other pregnancy-related issues in animal studies associated with any of the specific components of this vaccine? If yes, describe.</p> <p>3.2 Are there placental biology data for this vaccine's construct/platform or components? Describe</p>
B.4 Construct/Platform-specific questions
4.1 Are there pregnancy-related issues in clinical studies associated with any of the specific construct/platform of this vaccine? If yes, describe.
B.5 Antigen, adjuvant and other components-specific questions
5.1 Are there pregnancy-related issues in clinical studies associated with any of the antigen, adjuvant or other specific components of this vaccine? If yes, describe.
B.6 Construct/Platform-specific data in humans: non-pregnant population
6.1 Are there safety data from already licensed vaccines that use this specific vaccine in non-pregnant populations? If yes, describe
6.2 Are there safety data from clinical trials using this specific vaccine in non-pregnant populations even if not licensed? If yes, describe
B.7 Construct/Platform -specific efficacy data in humans: non-pregnant population
7.1 Describe mechanism/correlates of protection
7.2 Are there efficacy data from already licensed vaccines that use this specific vaccine in non-pregnant populations? If yes, describe
7.2 Are there efficacy data from clinical trials using this specific vaccine in non-pregnant populations even if not licensed? If yes, describe
B.8 Construct/Platform-specific safety data in humans: pregnant populations
8.1 Are there safety data from pregnant women in early clinical studies using this specific vaccine even if not licensed?
8.2 Are there safety data from inadvertently (in our outside clinical trials) exposed pregnant women?
8.3 Are there safety data from lactating women?
8.4 Are there pregnancy-related safety issues with this specific vaccine?
B.9 Construct/Platform-specific efficacy data in humans: pregnant population
9.1 Describe mechanisms/correlates of protection
9.2 Are there efficacy data from early clinical trials or PK/PD studies using this specific vaccine even if not licensed?

9.2 Are there efficacy data from inadvertently exposed pregnant women?
9.3 Are there efficacy data from lactating women?
9.4 Are there pregnancy-specific efficacy issues with this specific vaccine? If yes, describe.
B.10 Other vaccine components – Pregnancy-specific questions
10.1 What is known about the delivery system (eg. lipid nanoparticles) or other components of the vaccine in pregnancy?
10.2 What is known about transplacental transfer of these delivery systems and components?
10.3 What is known about permanence of vaccine delivery or other components in tissues?
B.11 Vaccine storage, delivery and administration characteristics
11.1 Is vaccine utilization in the context of antenatal care feasible?
10.1.1 Describe vaccine storage requirements in relation to antenatal care needs/settings
10.1.2 Describe vaccine administration requirements
10.1.3 Describe the number of doses needed and interval between doses
10.1.4 Describe specific considerations for vaccine administration in relation to other vaccines that are given during pregnancy (eg. Influenza, tetanus, pertussis).
10.1.5 Describe specific considerations for vaccine administration in relation to medications that are or could be given during pregnancy.

Section C. Key Questions on Development and Planning for All Candidate Vaccines (regardless of construct/platform) for Pregnant and Lactating Women and their Exposed Offspring
C. Vaccine Development Information
C.1. Pre-clinical Pregnancy Data
1.1 Are results of DART studies available or required?
1.1.1 DART studies date (or target date) of completion
1.1.2 Findings of DART studies (See also questions in Table 1. Section B.3)
C.2. Clinical Development status and plans for the vaccine in non-pregnant population
2.1 Target populations in clinical studies
2.1.1 Planned studies: planned total enrollment (answer for each: phase 1, phase 2, phase 3)
2.1.2 Ongoing studies: planned total enrollment (answer for each: phase 1, phase 2, phase 3)
2.1.3 Completed studies: total enrollment (answer for each: phase 1, phase 2, phase 3)
2.2 Location of clinical studies
2.2.1 In what countries are/will clinical studies be conducted?
2.2.2 Will studies be conducted in HIC and LMIC countries simultaneously?
2.2.3 Will approved vaccine be distributed in HIC and LMIC countries simultaneously?
2.2.4 Will vaccine be distributed in epidemic and/or endemic areas?
C.3. Safety data from non-pregnant population :
3.1 Vaccine reactogenicity (after each dose)
3.2 Adverse events following immunization (AEFIs)
3.3 Serious adverse events (SAEs)
3.4 Adverse events of special interest (AESIs)
3.5 Duration of safety follow up
C.4. Immunogenicity data from non-pregnant population:
4.1 Is there an accepted correlate of protection? (include assessment of quality of the data)
4.2 Antibody responses (include assessment of quality of the data)

4.3 Cell mediated immunity (Th1 vs. Th2) responses (include assessment of quality of the data)
4.4 Duration of immunity (include assessment of quality of the data)
4.4.1 How is immunity defined? (antibodies?, CMI? Other?)
4.4.2 What is the duration of follow up and protection
4.4 Is there a need for repeated immunizations?
C.5. What efficacy data are available from non-pregnant population?
5.1 Efficacy after partial vaccination?
5.2 Efficacy after complete vaccination?
C.6. Inadvertent pregnancy exposures in clinical studies in non-pregnant populations
6.1 Is there a plan for capture of data from women who become pregnant during the clinical trial? Describe plan or protocol, as well as mechanism for reporting outcomes
6.2 Will women who become pregnant during the clinical trial have the option to remain in the trial? Yes/no: explain rationale and plan.
6.3 What immunogenicity data are being/will be collected from women who become pregnant during the clinical trial?
6.3.1 Describe immunogenicity data, if any, collected to date
6.4 What safety data are being/will be collected from women who become pregnant during the clinical trial?
6.4.1 Describe safety data, if any, collected to date Include data collection forms and mechanism for reporting outcomes
6.5 What efficacy data are being/will be collected from women who become pregnant during the clinical studies?
6.5.1 Describe efficacy data, if any, collected to date.
6.6 What is the duration of follow-up for women who become pregnant in clinical trials? (include length and intervals of follow-up)
6.6.1 Describe follow-up data, if any, collected to date
6.7 What is the plan for collection of data from women in post-partum period?
6.7.1 Describe post-partum data, if any, collected to date.
6.8 What is the plan for follow up and collection of safety and efficacy data in infants of women who become pregnant in clinical trials?
6.8.1 Describe all infant data, if any, collected to date
C.7. Communication plan for inadvertent exposures in pregnant women
7.1 What is the plan to analyze and share the information from inadvertent pregnancy exposures to vaccine during clinical trials?
C.8. Inclusion of pregnant women in clinical trials
8.1 Is there a plan to extend enrollment of clinical studies to pregnant women?
○ If no, what is justification for exclusion?
○ If yes, describe plan in detail.
8.2 If yes, what is the plan for recruitment of pregnant women into clinical studies? Describe.
8.3 What immunogenicity data are being/will be collected from pregnant women in clinical studies?
8.3.1 Describe immunogenicity data, if any, collected to date
8.4 What safety data are being/will be collected from pregnant women in clinical studies?
8.4.1 Describe safety data, if any, collected to date
8.5 What efficacy data are being/will be collected from pregnant women in clinical studies?
8.5.1 Describe efficacy data, if any, collected to date.
8.6 Is there a plan for collection of data from women in post-partum period? If yes, describe. If no, explain.

8.7 Is there a plan for the collection and testing of breastmilk from post-partum women who were enrolled in clinical studies while pregnant? If yes, describe, If no, explain
8.8 Is there a plan for the collection and follow up of infants of women enrolled in clinical studies while pregnant? Describe protocol, safety, immunogenicity, efficacy data being collected, as well as duration of follow up.
C.9. Communication plan for pregnancy exposures in clinical studies
9.1 What is the plan to analyze and share the information from vaccine administration to pregnant women enrolled in clinical trials?
C.10. Plan for inclusion of lactating women in clinical trials
10.1 Is there a plan to extend clinical studies to lactating women? If yes, describe. If no, what is the justification for their exclusion?
10.2 Is there a plan for the collection and testing of breastmilk from lactating women enrolled in clinical studies? (See also questions in Section C.16)
C.11. Fetuses/neonates/infants:
11.1 What is the plan for capture of data from exposed fetuses of pregnant women enrolled in clinical studies?
11.2 What is the plan for capture of data from exposed neonates whose mothers were enrolled in clinical studies?
11.3 What is the plan for follow-up of exposed infants whose mothers were enrolled in clinical studies? Describe, including intervals and duration.
11.4 Will infant antibody titers be sequentially measured following birth to assess levels and duration after exposure? (See also questions in Section C.17.)
C.12. Vaccine approval for pregnant women
12.1 What outstanding data is needed for vaccine approval for pregnant women?
C.13. Pregnancy-specific safety questions
13.1 What reactogenicity is acceptable in pregnancy?
13.1.1 Proportion of subjects with fever, severity of fever, duration of fever
13.1.2 Local reactogenicity
13.1.3 Systemic reactogenicity
13.1.4 Other
C. 14. Timing of vaccination during pregnancy
14.1 What should be the preferred timing of vaccination during pregnancy and why?
14.2 Is the dosing schedule amenable to administration during pregnancy?
14.3 Can the full dose series be completed during pregnancy?
14.4 Can the dose series include pre- or post-pregnancy administration?
14.5 Can the dose series be administered with other vaccines given during pregnancy? What are the considerations for concomitant vaccination?
C.15. Adverse events in pregnant women
15.1 What adverse events following immunization (AEFIs) should be monitored?
○ Maternal
○ Obstetric
○ Fetal/neonatal
15.2 What outcomes of special interest (AESIs) should be monitored?
15.3 What is the risk for vaccine-associated enhanced disease (VAED)?
15.4 What is the risk for multisystem inflammatory syndrome in adults (MIS-A) or children (MIS-C)?

15.5 What is the risk for obstetric complications?
15.6 What is the risk for neonatal complications? Are infant AEs associated with gestational age and timing of exposure?
C.16. Lactation-specific questions
16.1 Is there a plan to test antibody concentration in breastmilk? Yes/No? If yes, describe.
16.2 Is there a plan to determine the effect of vaccine on lactating infant? Yes/No? If yes, describe.
16.3 Adverse events in lactating women: describe plan for evaluation
16.4 What adverse events following immunization (AEFIs) should be monitored in breastfed infants?
16.5 What outcomes of special interest (AESIs) should be monitored in breastfed infants?
C.17. Fetus/infant-specific questions
17.1 Is there a plan to determine if infant seroprotection is achieved following maternal immunization? Yes/No. Why? If yes, describe.
17.2 What is the ratio of maternal:infant antibody at delivery? (transplacental antibody passage)
17.3 What is the duration of maternally-derived antibody?
17.4 Effect of maternal antibody on natural disease in infants?
C.18. Adverse events in infants:
18.1 What adverse events following maternal immunization (AEFIs) should be monitored?
18.2 What outcomes of special interest (AESIs) should be monitored?
C.19. How long should infants exposed in utero be followed-up after birth?

Section D. Key Questions for Post-Licensure Safety Evaluation of Vaccine Use During Pregnancy
D.1. Who has access to detailed and timely post-licensure safety surveillance data?
D.2. General safety surveillance
2.1 What study designs should be considered for the assessment of vaccine safety post-licensure in addition to routine surveillance?
2.2 Are hospital-based systems or sentinel site-based approaches for safety surveillance feasible?
2.3 Is it feasible to do prospective safety studies of vaccinated women?
2.4 Is it feasible to do retrospective safety studies of vaccinated women?
2.5 How should passive safety surveillance systems be strengthened for signal detection?
2.6 What active safety surveillance approaches should be used to identify AESIs in LMICs?
D.3. Safety data questions for pregnancy exposures to approved for use or licensed vaccine
3.1 Was the vaccination recommended by a health care provider?
3.2 Details of vaccine administration, date, platform, construct, adjuvant (See sections B and C)
3.2.1 In what setting was the vaccine administered?
3.3 What, if any, are the known adverse events associated with use of the platform/construct/adjuvant?
3.4 When during pregnancy did vaccine exposure occur?
3.5 Can mother be linked to the child and any adverse outcomes in the newborn or neonate?
3.6 Can mother be linked to the child and any adverse outcomes in infant (12 months after birth)?
D.4. Adverse Events Following Immunization (AEFIs)/Adverse Events of Special Interest (AESIs)
4.1 What adverse outcomes or specific pregnancy outcomes or neonate outcomes of special interest (AESIs) should be monitored?
4.2 What safety outcomes or potential adverse events were identified during pre-clinical studies that should be studied post-approval?

4.3 Was any pregnancy related safety signal identified during vaccine previous clinical studies (clinical trials that recruited pregnant women, or those monitoring accidentally exposed pregnant women)?
4.4 What patient factors are important for the study population? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Examples: Age; Current or prior infections; HIV status; Obesity; Hypertension; Diabetes; Alcohol abuse; Substance abuse; Singleton versus multiple pregnancy; Prior pregnancy complications; Other factors? ○ Is prior infection a factor? Or an exclusion criterion? ○ Other factors?
D.5 Pregnancy Registries
5.1 Is/was there a pregnancy registry from prior use of candidate vaccine for other indications?
5.2 Is a post-licensure pregnancy registry in the development plan?
5.3 Will /was a pregnancy registry mandated by regulatory agencies?
5.4 Will the manufacturer be able to conduct a pregnancy registry in LMICs?
D.6. Active post-licensure studies
6.1 Are pharmacoepidemiology studies planned or established to identify or evaluate potential risks during the post-licensure period?
6.2 Are there other ongoing studies planned to follow-up on the pregnant or lactating women and their infants for 6 months to a year post-exposure to vaccination?
6.3 What other safety activities are/were recommended by regulatory authorities or the WHO?
D.7 Communication of Safety Findings
7.1 How will the findings of any safety studies be communicated to pregnant women?
7.2 How will the findings of any safety studies be communicated to the public?
7.3 How will the findings of any safety studies be communicated to other key stakeholders?
7.4 Do the communication plans include how to deal with misinformation and hesitancy regarding vaccine safety?
D.8 Vaccine Uptake
8.1 What is anticipated or known acceptance of the vaccine in general population?
8.2 What is anticipated or known acceptance of vaccines by pregnant women?
8.3 What is anticipated or known acceptance of the vaccine by pregnant population?
8.4 Will pregnant women choose to participate in vaccine clinical studies?
8.5 Will pregnant women choose to participate in post-licensure vaccine studies?

Section E. Summary Evaluation of the Candidate Vaccine for use During Pregnancy and Lactation
E.1. Key criteria to suggest vaccine for:
1.1 Pregnant women
1.2 Lactating women
E.2. Key criteria to reject vaccine for:
2.1 Pregnant women
2.2 Lactating women
E.3. Key considerations for proceeding with evaluation of a vaccine for:
3.1 Pregnant women
3.2 Lactating women

E.4. What safety data is needed for inclusion of pregnant women in clinical studies?
E.5. What efficacy data is needed for inclusion of pregnant women in clinical studies?
E.6. When in development phase should pregnant women be included?
E.7. What is the optimal timing of vaccination during pregnancy?
E.8. Has the communication plan been finalized and accepted by all involved parties?
8.1 Has the communication plan been implemented?

Conclusion

Because pregnant women are considered to be at high-risk for severe COVID-19 disease and potential adverse neonatal outcomes, it is imperative to permit and promote their participation in COVID-19 vaccine evaluation. Their inclusion in studies is critical to generate a robust database pre-licensure, and should continue in the post-licensure environment, to help identify vaccine candidates and licensed vaccines that are acceptable for use during pregnancy and lactation. Concerted efforts are needed to address fears that COVID-19 vaccines will be rushed to market prior to adequate safety evaluation. The Key Questions created by the MI WG will serve as a valuable tool for researchers and health care providers to assess new vaccines' suitability for pregnant and lactating women. Optimally pregnant and lactating women should be included in clinical vaccine trials to help guide regulatory and policy recommendations at the time of or shortly after licensure. Additionally, post-approval (e.g. under emergency or compassionate use authorization) or post-licensure surveillance studies are necessary in order to characterize the benefit-risk profile in larger pregnant and lactating women populations.

APPENDIX I. Maternal Immunization Working Group Composition

Table 1. COVAX Maternal Immunization WG Co-chairs: Flor Munoz, Ajoke Sobanjo-ter Meulen

WS – 1 PRODUCT MAPPING		WS -2 PRE-CLINICAL / CLINICAL		WS -3 VACCINE SAFETY	
Emily Erbeling (LEAD) Basic, translational and clinical Infectious disease and AIDS research	Director, Division of Microbiology and Infectious Diseases NIH/NIAID; US	Beate Kampmann (LEAD) Immunology, Vaccines, MI, clinical trials, epidemiology, research in LMIC	Professor of Paediatric Infection & Immunity; Director of the Vaccine Centre ; London School of Health and Tropical Medicine; UK	Stephen Anderson (LEAD) Statistics of vaccine safety and evaluation, Regulatory, MI	Director, Office of Biostatistics and Epidemiology CBER/WHO-GAVCS; US
Ajoke Sobanjo-ter Meulen MI Clinical vaccine development	Senior Program Officer, Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation; US	Flor Munoz-Rivas MI clinical trials, Vaccine safety, GAIA case definitions	Associate Professor, Pediatrics-Infectious Disease; Baylor College of Medicine; US	Andy Stergachis (LEAD) MI pharmacovigilance, vaccine safety, pregnancy registries	Professor, Global Health; Professor, Pharmacy Director, Global Medicines Program University of Washington; US
Karin Bok Vaccine research development, policy	Senior Advisor Vaccine Development, VRC, NIAID, NIH; US	Geeta Swamy NVAC and VRBPAC; OB/GYN physician	Associate Professor of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Duke University School of Medicine; US		
Anh Wartel Vaccine development, epidemiology, South East Asia region	Associate Director General of Clinical Development, IVI, South Korea	Clare Cutland MI Vaccine clinical trials, implementation	Lecturer, University of the Witwatersand; South Africa	Steve Black Vaccine safety, safety surveillance	CEPI-SPEAC; US
Angela Gentile Infectious diseases and maternal immunization research in LAM	Head, Department of Epidemiology, Ricardo Gutiérrez Children's Hospital; Argentina	Asma Khalil Obstetrician, maternal-fetal medicine, vaccine studies, MI, RCOG member	Professor, Consultant obstetrician at St George's Hospital, UK	Delese Mimi Darko Regulatory, pharmacovigilance	Chief Executive Office, Ghana Food and Drugs Authority; Ghana
Gerald Voss Vaccine development	Scientific Director of the Tuberculosis Vaccine Initiative/ CEPI; Belgium	Helen Marshall Vaccines, MI, clinical trials, epidemiology, implementation, regulatory	Medical Director VIRTU & A-Prof Vaccinology Affiliate Lecturer, Women's and Children's Health / Public Health; University of Adelaide; Australia	Christine Guillard Clinical trials, Vaccine safety, Pregnancy surveillance	Global Vaccine Safety Initiative; WHO
Johan Vekemans Maternal Immunization	SARS-CoV-2 vaccine Global Clinical Head, AstraZeneca; Belgium	Chrissie Jones Vaccines, MI, clinical trials, infectious diseases	Associate Professor in Paediatric Infectious Diseases and Immunology, University of Southampton; UK	Esperanca Sevene Pharmacovigilance, Epidemiology and vaccine research in LMIC, Pregnancy registries	Associate Professor, Universidade Eduardo Mondlane; Mozambique
Titilope Odeyebo CDC Pregnancy Birth Defects Task Force	CDC; US ACOG, IIFPHPEWG	Sylvanus Okogbenin Obstetrician, epidemiology, Lassa fever/EID in pregnancy	Professor, Consultant Obstetrician, Irrua Specialist Teaching Hospital; Nigeria		
		Judith Absalon	Senior Director ,Vaccines Clinical Research, Pfizer; US		
Cross-cutting advisors					
Marion Gruber (Regulatory) Regulatory, MI	Director, Center for Biologics Evaluation and Research (CBER) FDA; US	Helen Rees (Regulatory) Pregnancy registry, HIV/reproductive health, MI safety, regulatory	Professor, Wits Reproductive Health and HIV Institute, Board Chair SAHPRA; South Africa	Daniel Brasseur (Regulatory/CEPI)	Former CHMP-PDCO-VWP chair at EMA; CEPI consultant; EU
Ruth Karron (Ethics) Ethics of MI research	Professor, Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health; US	Carleigh Krubiner (Ethics)	Policy Fellow, Center for Global Development, Johns Hopkins Univ; US		

APPENDIX II

Brighton Collaboration Standardized Templates for the Benefit-Risk Assessment of Vaccines

Brighton Collaboration Viral Vector Vaccines Safety Working Group (V3SWG)

Brighton Collaboration Benefit-Risk Assessment of Vaccines by Technology (BRAVATO) Working Group

The latest version of these templates can be accessed at <https://brightoncollaboration.us/bravato/>.

Please read the specific instructions prior to completing the templates. Contact the Brighton Collaboration here:

brightoncollaborationv3swg@gmail.com

APPENDIX V.A – Nucleic Acid (RNA and DNA) Vaccines

A. Brighton Collaboration Standardized Template for Risk Assessment of Nucleic Acid (RNA and DNA) Vaccines		
1. Authorship	Information	
1.1 Author(s) and affiliation(s)		
1.2. Date completed/updated		
2. Basic Vaccine information	Inform-ation	Comments/Concerns
2.1 Vaccine name		
2.2 Nucleic Acid Type: DNA, RNA, self-amplifying RNA		
2.3 Adjuvant (if applicable)		
2.4 Final vaccine formulation components that may impact delivery into cells, stability, and safety (e.g. complexing with polymers, encapsulation within microparticles, liposomes)		
2.5 Route and method of delivery (e.g. intramuscular injection, gene gun, electroporation)		
3. Target Pathogen and Population		
3.1 What is the target pathogen?		
3.2 What are the disease manifestations caused by the target pathogen in humans, for the following categories:		
• In healthy people		
• In immunocompromised people		
• In neonates, infants, children		
• During pregnancy and in the fetus		
• In elderly		
• In any other special populations		
3.3 Briefly, what are the key epidemiologic characteristics of the disease caused by the target pathogen (e.g. incubation period, communicable period, route/s of transmission, case fatality rate, transmissibility characteristics such as basic reproductive ratio (R_0), and spontaneous mutation)?		
3.4 What sections of the population are most affected by the target pathogen (e.g. pediatric, pregnant, lactating women (breast-feeding), adult, elderly)?		
3.5 What is known about the immune responses, duration, and potential correlates of protective immunity to the target pathogen or to the disease?		
3.6 Please describe any other key information about the target pathogen or population that may inform benefit-risk		
4. Characteristics of Vaccine Transgene and Expression		
4.1 Nature of the nucleic acid platform (DNA - synthetic, bacterial, plasmid, linear, >1 type/molecule, other; RNA - messenger, self-replicating, other)		

4.2 Gene(s) incorporated into the vaccine (antigen, T-cell epitopes, antibiotic resistance factors, cytokines, other)		
4.3 Factors enhancing/controlling gene expression		
4.4 Non-expressed features impacting vaccine efficacy (CpG sequences, other)		
4.5 Other sequence features that may impact safety (e.g. sequences in DNA that might facilitate insertion or recombination)		
4.6 Is the transgene likely to induce immunity to all strains/genotypes of the target pathogen?		
4.7 What is known about the immune response to the vaccine in animals and/or humans (binding, functional, and neutralizing antibody, B-cell, T-cell memory, etc.)?		
5. Delivery and Administration		
5.1 Describe how components of the vaccine formulation that facilitate stability* and delivery into cells (Section 2.4) impact the safety profile of the vaccine?		
* Stability is considered here in the context of any relevant intrinsic characteristic of the vaccine deemed important for safety purposes. For example, among the risks that WHO, FDA, and EMA list for the use of DNA vaccines is the hazard of integration into recipient's chromosomal DNA with the resulting risk of insertional mutagenesis or spreading of antibiotics resistance genes. The probability of chromosomal integration increases if the introduced pDNA has been linearized, and this is the reason that regulatory authorities require the plasmid preparation intended for vaccination or gene therapy to contain a high percentage of supercoiled material (usually >80%). The percentage of supercoiled material is also used as a criterion of DNA vaccine stability at different storage temperatures.		
5.2 Describe how the mode of vaccine delivery may impact safety* (e.g., electroporation (please specify name of device), intradermal needle injection)		
* Also consider the safety impact of multi-dose delivery methods, the use of multi dose vaccine vials, and any special considerations for disposal.		
5.3 How might any co-administered components (e.g. adjuvants, cytokines, immunomodulatory molecules) impact the safety profile?		
5.4 If applicable, describe the heterologous prime-boost regimen that this vaccine is a part of and the possible impact on safety		
6. Toxicology and Nonclinical		
6.1 What is known about biodistribution of the platform nucleic acid in its final formulation and mode of administration in animal models?		
6.2 How long does the RNA or DNA persist in vivo (may specify in tissue/serum, proximal/distal to site of administration)?		
6.3 What is the risk of integration of sequences from the platform nucleic acid into the host genome?		
6.4 What is the possible risk of autoimmunity or a harmful immune response?		
6.5 Summarize the preclinical safety data that supports the use of this product in humans including any related information from similar products		
6.6 Summarize the preclinical immunogenicity and efficacy data that supports the use of this product in humans including any related information from similar products		
6.7 What is the evidence of disease enhancement (including antibody dependent enhancement (ADE), vaccine associated enhanced respiratory disease (VAERD).) or absence thereof <i>in vitro</i> or in animal models? ¹⁴		

6.8 Would the vaccine in its final formulation have any impact on innate immunity? If so, what are the implications for benefit- risk?		
7. Human Efficacy and Other Important Information		
7.1 What is the evidence that the vaccine would generate a protective immune response in humans (e.g. natural history, passive immunization, animal challenge studies)?		
7.2 Describe other key information that may impact benefit-risk		
8. Adverse Event (AE) Assessment of the Vaccine Platform (*see Instructions):		
8.1 Approximately how many humans have received this vaccine to date? If variants of the vaccine platform, please list separately _____		
8.2 Method(s) used for safety monitoring:		
• Spontaneous reports/passive surveillance Yes/No? If yes describe method:		
• Diary – Yes/No? If yes, number of days		
• Other active surveillance – Yes/No? if yes, describe method (e.g., LTFU) and list the AES solicited:		
8.3 What criteria were used for grading the AEs?		
• 2007 US FDA Guidance for Industry Toxicity Grading Scale for Healthy Adult and Adolescent Volunteers Enrolled in Preventive Vaccine Clinical Trials. Yes/No		
• If no criteria were used for grading, or if other metrics were employed, please describe:		
8.4 List and provide frequency of any related or possibly related serious* AEs and well as any severe expected or unexpected AEs observed: (*see Instructions):		
8.5 List and provide frequency of any serious, unexpected significantly increased AE or lab abnormality in vaccine vs. control groups:		
• Describe the control group: _____.		
8.6 List and provide frequency of Adverse Events of Special Interest		
8.7 What is the evidence of disease enhancement (including antibody dependent enhancement (ADE), vaccine associated enhanced respiratory disease (VAERD)) (if any) in humans?		
8.8 Did a Data Safety Monitoring Board (DSMB) or its equivalent oversee the study? Yes/No?		
• Did it identify any safety issue of concern? Yes/No? If yes, describe.		
9. Overall Risk Assessment		
9.1 Please summarize key safety issues of concern identified to date, if any:		
• how should they be addressed going forward		
9.2 What is the potential for causing serious unwanted effects and toxicities in:(Describe the toxicities) (Please rate risk as: none, minimal, low, moderate, high, or unknown)		
• healthy humans?		

• immunocompromised humans?		
• human neonates, infants, children?		
• pregnancy and in the fetus in humans?		
• elderly?		
• in any other special populations (e.g., institutionalized people, individuals with associated chronic comorbidity)?		
References		

APPENDIX V.B – Protein Vaccines

B. Brighton Collaboration Standardized Template for Risk Assessment of Protein Vaccine Candidates		
1. Authorship	Inform-ation	Comments /Concerns
1.1 Author(s) and affiliation(s)		
1.2 Date completed/updated		
2. Basic Vaccine information		
2.1 Vaccine name		
2.2 Protein type (e.g., molecular clamp, virus-like particle, peptide) and any special characteristics		
2.3 Type of heterologous expression system used for antigen production (e.g., bacteria, yeast, plants, mammalian or insect cells, chemical synthesis)		
2.4 Adjuvant (if applicable)		
2.5 Final vaccine formulation components that may impact delivery into cells, stability, and safety (e.g., preservatives (e.g., thimerosal, phenol, benzethonium chloride, 2-phenoxyethanol), complexing with polymers, encapsulation within microparticles, liposomes, depot formulations)		
2.6 Route and method of delivery (e.g., intramuscular injection, microneedles, skin patch, intranasal, other mucosal)		
3. Target Pathogen and Population		
3.1 What is the target pathogen?		
3.2 What are the disease manifestations caused by the target pathogen in humans, for the following categories:		
In healthy people		
In immunocompromised people		
In neonates, infants, children		
During pregnancy and in the fetus		

In elderly		
In any other special populations		
3.3 Briefly, what are the key epidemiologic characteristics of the disease caused by the target pathogen (e.g., incubation period, communicable period, route/s of transmission, case fatality rate, transmissibility characteristics such as basic reproductive ratio (R_0), and spontaneous mutation)?		
3.4 What sections of the population are most affected by the target pathogen (e.g., pediatric, pregnant, lactating women (breast feeding), adult, elderly)		
3.5 What is known about the immune responses, duration, and potential correlates of protective immunity to the target pathogen or to the disease?		
3.6 Please describe any other key information about the target pathogen or population that may inform benefit-risk		
4. Characteristics of Antigen		
4.1 Is the vaccine likely to induce immunity to all strains/genotypes of the target pathogen? What is the evidence?		
4.2 What is known about the immune response to the vaccine in animals and/or humans (binding, functional, and neutralizing antibody, B-cell, T-cell memory, etc.)?		
4.3 Is there homology in the sequence of the vaccine antigen and human proteins?		
5. Adjuvant (if applicable)		
5.1 Describe the type of adjuvant, if it has been tested in humans, whether novel or commercialized, and if applicable, what other vaccines (preventive and therapeutic) are formulated with this adjuvant		
5.2 What is the evidence that an adjuvant improves/boosts/enhances the immune response?		
5.3 What is the mechanism of action of the adjuvant (if known)?		
5.4 How is the adjuvant formulated with the antigen?		
5.5 How might the adjuvant impact the safety profile of the vaccine?		
5.6 Summarize the safety findings (preclinical and clinical) with the adjuvant, formulated with any antigen		
6. Delivery and Administration		
6.1 How might the vaccine formulation (antigen and adjuvant already formulated in the same vial or combined prior to administration) impact the safety profile of the vaccine?		
6.2 If the vaccine is part of a heterologous prime-boost regimen, describe the regimen that this vaccine is a part of and the possible impact on safety		
6.3 Describe how components of the vaccine formulation that facilitate stability and delivery into cells (Section 2.5) may impact the safety profile of the vaccine		
6.4 Describe how the mode of vaccine delivery may impact safety (e.g., intramuscular by needle injection, microneedles, intranasal, oral)		
* stability is considered here in the context of any relevant intrinsic characteristic of the vaccine deemed important for safety purpose.		
7. Toxicology and Nonclinical		
7.1 What is known about biodistribution of the antigen in its final formulation and mode of administration in animal models?		
7.2 How long does the vaccine antigen persist in vivo (may specify in tissue/serum; proximal/distal to site of administration)?		

7.3 What is the possible risk of autoimmunity or a harmful immune response?		
7.4 Summarize the preclinical safety data that support the use of this product in humans including any related information from similar products		
7.5 Summarize the preclinical immunogenicity and efficacy data that support the use of this product in humans including any related information from similar products		
7.6 What is the evidence of disease enhancement or absence thereof <i>in vitro</i> or in animal models? ⁸		
7.7 Would the vaccine in its final formulation have any impact on innate immunity? If so, what are the implications for benefit-risk?		
8. Human Efficacy and Other Important Information		
8.1 What is the evidence that the vaccine would generate a protective immune response in humans (e.g., natural history, passive immunization, animal challenge studies)?		
8.2 Describe other key information that may impact benefit-risk		
9. Adverse Event (AE) Assessment of the Vaccine Platform (*see Instructions):		
9.1 Approximately how many humans have received this vaccine to date? If variants of the vaccine platform, please list separately. _____		
9.2 Method(s) used for safety monitoring:		
Spontaneous reports/passive surveillance		
Diary		
Other active surveillance		
9.3 What criteria were used for grading the AEs?		
2007 US FDA Guidance for Industry Toxicity Grading Scale for Healthy Adult and Adolescent Volunteers Enrolled in Preventive Vaccine Clinical Trials		
If no criteria were used for grading, or if other metrics were employed, please describe:		
9.4 List and provide frequency of any or possibly related serious* AEs and well as any severe expected or unexpected AEs observed: (*see Instructions):		
9.5 List and provide frequency of any serious, unexpected significantly increased AE or lab abnormality in vaccine vs. control groups:		
Describe the control group: _____.		
9.6. List and provide frequency of Adverse Events of Special Interest		
9.7 What is the evidence of disease enhancement (if any) in humans?		
9.8 Did a Data Safety Monitoring Board (DSMB) or its equivalent oversee the study?		
Did it identify any safety issue of concern?		
If so describe:		
10. Overall Risk Assessment		
10.1 Please summarize key safety issues of concern identified to date, if any:		
how should they be addressed going forward		
10.2 What is the potential for causing serious unwanted effects and toxicities in:		

healthy humans?		
immunocompromised humans?		
human neonates, infants, children?		
pregnancy and in the fetus in humans?		
elderly?		
in any other special populations (e.g., institutionalized population, individuals with associated chronic comorbidity)?		
References		

APPENDIX V.C – Viral Vector Vaccine Candidates

C. Brighton Collaboration Standardized Template for Risk Assessment of Viral Vector Vaccine Candidates		
1. Authorship and Affiliation	Inform- ation	Comments /Concerns
1.1. Author(s) and affiliation		
1.2. Date completed/updated		
2. Basic vector information		
2.1 Vector name		
2.2. Vector origin Family/Genus/Species/subtype		
2.3. Vector replication in humans (replicating or non-replicating)		
3. Characteristics of the wild type virus from which the vector is derived		
3.1 Name of wild type virus (common name; Family/Genus/Species/subtype)		
3.2 What is the natural host for the wild type virus?		
3.3. How is the wild type virus normally transmitted?		
3.4. Does the wild type virus establish a latent or persistent infection?		
3.5. Does the wild type virus replicate in the nucleus?		
3.6. What is the risk of integration into the human genome?		
3.7. List any disease manifestations caused by the wild type virus, the strength of evidence, severity, and duration of disease for the following categories:		
In the healthy natural host		
In laboratory hosts (specify species)		
In healthy human host		
In immunocompromised humans		
In breast milk, human neonates, infants, children		
During pregnancy and in the unborn in humans		
In any other special populations?		
3.8. What cell types are infected and what receptors are used in the natural host and in humans?		

3.9. What is known about the mechanisms of immunity to the wild type virus?		
3.10 Has disease enhancement (including antibody dependent enhancement (ADE), vaccine associated enhanced respiratory disease (VAERD)) been demonstrated with the wild type virus:		
● in vitro?		
● in animal models?		
● in human hosts?		
3.11 Is disease enhancement (including antibody dependent enhancement (ADE), vaccine associated enhanced respiratory disease (VAERD)) a possible vaccine-induced contributor to the pathogenesis of wild type disease		
3.12 What is the background prevalence of natural immunity to the virus?		
3.13 Is there any vaccine available for the wild-type virus? If yes,		
● What populations are immunized?		
● What is the background prevalence of artificial immunity?		
3.14 Is there treatment available for the disease caused by the wild type virus		
4. Characteristics of the vector from which vaccine(s) may be derived		
4.1 Describe the source of the vector (e.g., isolation, synthesis)		
4.2. What is the basis of attenuation/inactivation of the wild type virus to create the vector?		
4.3. What is known about the replication, transmission and pathogenicity of the vector in humans in the following categories:		
in healthy people		
in immunocompromised people		
in breast milk, neonates, infants, children		
during pregnancy and in the fetus		
in gene therapy experiments		
in any other special populations		
4.4. Is the vector replication-competent in non-human species?		
4.5. What is the risk of reversion to virulence, recombination or reassortment with wild type virus or other agents?		
4.6 Is the vector genetically stable in vitro and/or in vivo?		
4.7. What is the potential for shedding and transmission, including arthropod borne transmission, to humans or other species?		
4.8. Does the vector establish a latent or persistent infection?		
4.9. Does the vector replicate in the nucleus?		
4.10. What is the risk of integration into the human genome?		
4.11. Is there any previous human experience with this or a similar vector (safety and immunogenicity records)?		
4.12. What cell types are infected and what receptors are used in humans?		
4.13. What is known about the mechanisms of immunity to the vector?		
4.14 Has disease enhancement (including antibody dependent enhancement (ADE), vaccine associated enhanced respiratory disease (VAERD)) been demonstrated with the vector?		

● in vitro?		
● in animal models?		
● in human hosts?		
4.15. Is there antiviral treatment available for disease manifestations caused by the vector?		
4.16. Can the vector accommodate multigenic inserts or will several vectors be required for multigenic vaccines?		
5. Toxicology and Potency (Pharmacology) of the Vector		
5.1. What is known about the replication, transmission and pathogenicity of the vector in and between animals?		
5.2. For replicating vectors, has a comparative virulence and viral kinetic study been conducted in permissive and susceptible species? (yes/no) If not, what species would be used for such a study? Is it feasible to conduct such a study?		
5.3. Does an animal model relevant to assess attenuation exist?		
5.4. Does an animal model for safety including immuno-compromised animals exist?		
5.5. Does an animal model for reproductive toxicity exist?		
5.6. Does an animal model for immunogenicity and efficacy exist?		
5.7. Does an animal model for antibody enhanced disease (including antibody dependent enhancement (ADE), vaccine associated enhanced respiratory disease (VAERD)) or immune complex disease exist?		
5.8. What is known about biodistribution in animal models or in humans, including neurovirulence and/or neuroinvasion?		
5.9. What is the evidence that vector derived vaccines will generate a beneficial immune response in:		
Small animal models?		
Nonhuman primates (NHP)?		
Human?		
5.10. Have challenge or efficacy studies been conducted in subjects with:		
Immunocompromised conditions including HIV?		
Other diseases?		
5.11. Have studies been done simultaneously or sequentially administering more than one vector with different transgenes? Is there evidence for interaction/interference?		
6. Adverse Event (AE) Assessment of the Vector (*see Instructions):		
6.1. Approximately how many humans have received any vaccine using this viral vector to date? If variants of the vector, please list separately. _____		
6.2. Method(s) used for safety monitoring:		
Spontaneous reports/passive surveillance: Yes/No – If yes, describe method		
Diary: Yes/No – If yes, number of days: Yes/No – If yes, describe method and list the AE's solicited		
Other active surveillance		
6.3. What criteria were used for grading the AE's?		
2007 US FDA Guidance for Industry Toxicity Grading Scale for Healthy Adult and Adolescent Volunteers Enrolled in Preventive Vaccine Clinical Trials -- Yes/No		

If no criteria were used for grading, or if other metrics were employed, please describe:		
6.4. List and provide frequency of any related or possibly related serious* AE's as well as any severe, expected or unexpected AE observed: (*see Instructions):		
6.5. List and provide frequency of any serious, unexpected significantly increased AE or lab abnormality in vaccinee vs. control group:		
Describe the control group: _____.		
6.6. List and provide frequency of Adverse Events of Special Interest		
6.7. Did a Data Safety Monitoring Board (DSMB) or its equivalent oversee the study? Yes/No		
Did it identify any safety issue of concern? Yes/No		
If so describe:		
7. Overall Risk Assessment of the Vector		
7.1. Please summarize key safety issues of concern identified to date, if any:		
how should they be addressed going forward:		
7.2. What is the potential for causing serious unwanted effects and toxicities in:		
- healthy humans? -- Describe toxicities – Please rate risk as: none, minimal, ow, moderate, high, or unknown		
- immunocompromised humans? -- Describe toxicities – Please rate risk as: none, minimal, ow, moderate, high, or unknown		
- Breast milk, human neonates, infants, children? -- Describe toxicities – Please rate risk as: none, minimal, ow, moderate, high, or unknown		
- pregnancy and in the fetus in humans? -- Describe toxicities – Please rate risk as: none, minimal, ow, moderate, high, or unknown		
- Elderly -- Describe toxicities – Please rate risk as: none, minimal, ow, moderate, high, or unknown		
in any other special populations (e.g., institutionalized population, individuals with associated chronic comorbidity)? Describe toxicities – Please rate risk as: none, minimal, ow, moderate, high, or unknown		
7.3. What is the potential for shedding and transmission in risk groups?		
8. Target Pathogen and Population for the vaccine		
8.1 What is the target pathogen for the vaccine?		
8.2 What are the disease manifestations caused by the target pathogen in humans, for the following categories:		
- In healthy people		
- In immunocompromised people		
- In neonates, infants, children		
- During pregnancy and in the fetus		
- In elderly		
- In any other special populations		

8.3 Briefly, what are the key epidemiologic characteristics of the disease caused by the target pathogen (e.g., incubation period, communicable period, route/s of transmission, case fatality rate, transmissibility characteristics such as basic reproductive ratio (R_0), and intrinsic mutation)?		
8.4 What sections of the population are most affected by the target pathogen (e.g., pediatric, pregnant, lactating women (breast feeding), adult, elderly)		
8.5 What is known about the immune responses, duration, and potential correlates of protective immunity to the target pathogen or to the disease?		
8.6 Please describe any other key information about the target pathogen or population that may inform benefit-risk		
9. Characteristics of the Vaccine		
9.1 Vaccine name		
9.2. What is the identity and source of the transgene?		
9.3. Is the transgene likely to induce immunity to all strains/genotypes of the target pathogen?		
9.4. Where in the vector genome is the transgene inserted?		
9.5. Does the insertion of the transgene involve deletion or other rearrangement of any vector genome sequences?		
9.6. How is the transgene expression controlled (transcriptional promoters, etc.)?		
9.7. Does insertion or expression of the transgene affect the pathogenicity or phenotype of the vector?		
9.8. Is the vaccine replication-competent in humans or other species?		
9.9. What is the risk of reversion to virulence, recombination or reassortment with wild type virus or other agents?		
9.10. Is the vaccine genetically stable in vitro and/or in vivo?		
9.11. What is the potential for shedding and transmission to humans or other species?		
9.12. Does the vaccine establish a latent or persistent infection?		
9.13. Does the vaccine replicate in the nucleus?		
9.14. What is the risk of integration into the human genome?		
9.15. List any disease manifestations caused by the vaccine in humans, the strength of evidence, severity, and duration of disease for the following categories:		
In healthy people		
In immunocompromised people		
In breast milk, neonates, infants, children		
During pregnancy and in the fetus		
In any other special populations		
9.16. What cell types are infected and what receptors are used in humans?		
9.17. What is known about the mechanisms of immunity to the vaccine?		
9.18 Has disease enhancement (including antibody dependent enhancement (ADE), vaccine associated enhanced respiratory disease (VAERD)) been demonstrated with the vaccine?		
● in vitro?		
● in animal models?		
● in human hosts?		

9.19 What is known about the effect of pre-existing immunity, including both natural immunity and repeat administration of the vector or the vaccine, on 'take', safety or efficacy in any animal model or human studies using this vector?		
9.20. Is the vaccine transmissible in humans or other species (including arthropods) and/or stable in the environment?		
9.21. Are there antiviral or other treatments available for disease manifestations caused by the vaccine?		
9.22. Vaccine formulation		
9.23. Proposed route and method of vaccine delivery (e.g., oral, intramuscular injection microneedles, skin patch, intranasal, mucosal)		
9.24. Target populations for the vaccine (e.g., pediatric, maternal, adult, elderly etc.)		
10. Toxicology and Potency (Pharmacology) of the Vaccine		
10.1. What is known about the replication, transmission and pathogenicity of the vaccine in and between animals?		
10.2. For replicating vectors, has a comparative virulence and viral kinetic study been conducted in permissive and susceptible species? (yes/no) If not, what species would be used for such a study? Is it feasible to conduct such a study?		
10.3. Does an animal model relevant to assess attenuation exist?		
10.4. Does an animal model for safety including immuno-compromised animals exist?		
10.5. Does an animal model for reproductive toxicity exist?		
10.6. Does an animal model for immunogenicity and efficacy exist?		
10.7 Does an animal model for antibody enhanced disease (including antibody dependent enhancement (ADE), vaccine associated enhanced respiratory disease (VAERD)) or immune complex disease exist?		
10.8. What is known about biodistribution in animal models or in humans, including neurovirulence and/or neuroinvasion?		
10.9 What is the evidence that vector derived vaccines will generate a beneficial immune response in:		
Small animal models?		
Nonhuman primates (NHP)?		
Human?		
10.10. Have challenge or efficacy studies been conducted in subjects with:		
Immunocompromised conditions including HIV?		
Other diseases?		
10.11 Have studies been done simultaneously or sequentially administering more than one vector with different transgenes? Is there evidence for interaction/interference?		
11. Adverse Event (AE) Assessment of the Vaccine (*see Instructions):		
11.1. Approximately how many humans have received this viral vector vaccine to date? If variants of the vector, please list separately. _____		
11.2. Method(s) used for safety monitoring:		
Spontaneous reports/passive surveillance: Yes/No, if yes, describe method		
Diary: Yes/No, if yes, number of days		

Other active surveillance : Yes/No, If yes, describe method and list the AE's solicited		
11.3. What criteria were used for grading the AE's?		
2007 US FDA Guidance for Industry Toxicity Grading Scale for Healthy Adult and Adolescent Volunteers Enrolled in Preventive Vaccine Clinical Trials: Yes/No		
If no criteria were used for grading, or if other metrics were employed, please describe:		
11.4. List and provide frequency of any related or possibly related serious* AE's as well as any severe, expected or unexpected AE observed: (*see Instructions):		
11.5. List and provide frequency of any serious, unexpected significantly increased AE or lab abnormality in vaccinee vs. control group:		
Describe the control group: _____.		
11.6. List and provide frequency of Adverse Events of Special Interest		
11.7. Did a Data Safety Monitoring Board (DSMB) or its equivalent oversee the study? Yes/No		
Did it identify any safety issue of concern? Yes/No		
If so describe:		
12. Overall Risk Assessment of the Vaccine		
12.1. Please summarize key safety issues of concern identified to date, if any: how should they be addressed going forward:		
12.2. What is the potential for causing serious unwanted effects and toxicities in:		
- healthy humans? Describe toxicities – Please rate risk as: none, minimal, ow, moderate, high, or unknown		
- immunocompromised humans? - Describe toxicities – Please rate risk as: none, minimal, ow, moderate, high, or unknown		
- Breast milk, human neonates, infants, children? Describe toxicities – Please rate risk as: none, minimal, ow, moderate, high, or unknown		
- pregnancy and in the fetus in humans? Describe toxicities – Please rate risk as: none, minimal, ow, moderate, high, or unknown		
- elderly? Describe toxicities – Please rate risk as: none, minimal, ow, moderate, high, or unknown		
- in any other special populations (e.g., institutionalized population, individuals with associated chronic comorbidity)? Describe toxicities – Please rate risk as: none, minimal, ow, moderate, high, or unknown		
12.3. What is the potential for shedding and transmission in risk groups?		
13. Any other information concerning either the viral vector or the vaccine		
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APPENDIX V.D – Live Attenuated Viral Vaccines

D. Brighton Collaboration Standardized Template for Risk Assessment of Live Attenuated Viral Vaccines ⁴¹		
1. Authorship	Inform-ation	Comments /Concerns
1.1 Author(s) and affiliation(s)		
1.2 Date completed/updated		
2. Basic Vaccine information		
2.1 Vaccine name		
2.2 Virus name, genus, family strains/serotypes, origin (e.g., geography, patient, asymptomatic infection), and any other specific characteristics, such as genetic modifications		
2.3 Method of attenuation		
2.4 Substrate for vaccine virus growth and method of production (e.g., nature of substrate, cell line, eggs, bioreactor, microcarriers, etc.)		
2.5 Final vaccine formulation components		
2.6 Route and method of delivery (e.g., oral, intramuscular injection, microneedles, skin patch, intranasal, other mucosal)		
3. Target Pathogen and Population		
3.1 What is the target pathogen?		
3.2 What are the disease manifestations caused by the target pathogen in humans, for the following categories:		
In healthy people		
In immunocompromised people		
In neonates, infants, children		
During pregnancy and in the fetus		
In elderly		
In any other special populations		
3.3 Briefly, what are the key epidemiologic characteristics of the disease caused by the target pathogen (e.g., incubation period, communicable period, route/s of transmission, case fatality rate, transmissibility characteristics such as basic reproductive ratio (R0), and extent of natural mutation)?		

3.4 Does the target pathogen establish a latent or persistent infection?		
3.5 Does the target pathogen virus replicate in the nucleus?		
3.6 What is the risk of integration into the human genome?		
3.7 What sections of the population are most affected by the target pathogen (e.g., pediatric, pregnant, lactating women (breast feeding), adult, elderly)		
3.8 What is known about the immune responses, duration, and potential correlates of protective immunity to the target pathogen or to the disease?		
3.9 Please describe any other key information about the target pathogen or population that may inform benefit-risk		
4. Characteristics of Attenuated Vaccine Virus		
4.1 Describe the source of the virus or virus strains (e.g., isolation, synthesis)		
4.2. How does attenuated virus differ from the pathogen?		
Method of attenuation and validation		
4.3 Does the vaccine establish a latent or persistent infection?		
4.4 Does the vaccine virus replicate in the nucleus?		
4.5 What is the risk of integration into the human genome?		
4.6. What is known about the replication of vaccine virus in humans in the following categories:		
in healthy people		
in immunocompromised people		
in neonates, infants, children		
during pregnancy and in the fetus		
in any other special populations		
4.7. What is the risk of reversion to virulence, recombination or reassortment with wild type virus or other agents?		
4.8. What is the potential for shedding and transmission to humans or other species?		
4.9 Is the vaccine virus genetically stable in vitro and/or in vivo?		
5. Delivery and Administration		
5.1 How might the vaccine formulation (antigen and diluent and/or any other co-administered component formulated in the same vial or combined prior to administration) impact the safety profile of the vaccine?		

5.2 If applicable, describe the heterologous prime-boost regimen that this vaccine is a part of and the possible impact on safety		
5.3 Describe how components of the vaccine formulation that facilitate stability* and delivery into cells (Section 2.5) impact the safety profile of the vaccine		
5.4 Describe how the mode of vaccine delivery may impact safety (e.g., intramuscular by needle injection, microneedles, intranasal, oral, or combination thereof)		
* stability is considered here in the context of any relevant intrinsic characteristic of the vaccine deemed relevant for safety purpose.		
6. Toxicology and Nonclinical		
6.1 Will the vaccine virus express or replicate in non-human species?		
6.2 Summarize the preclinical safety data that supports the use of this product in humans including any related information from similar products		
6.3 Summarize the preclinical immunogenicity and efficacy data that supports the use of this product in humans including any related information from similar products		
6.4 What is the evidence of disease enhancement or absence thereof in vitro or in animal models? ¹³		
6.5 Would the vaccine in its final formulation have any impact on innate immunity? If so, what are the implications for benefit-risk?		
6.6 What is the evidence that the vaccine has generated a beneficial immune response in:		
o Animal models?		
o Nonhuman primates (NHP)?		
7. Human Efficacy and Other Important Information		
7.1 What is known about the replication of vaccine virus in humans in the following categories:		
in healthy people		
in immunocompromised people		
in neonates, infants, children		
during pregnancy and in the fetus		
in gene therapy experiments		
in any other special populations		
7.2 What is the evidence that the vaccine generates a protective immune response in humans (e.g., natural history, passive immunization, animal challenge studies)?		
7.3 Can the vaccine virus protect against multiple strains or serotypes or will separate strains be required for multigenic vaccines?		

Was there evidence generated?		
What is known about the immune response to the vaccine in animals and/or humans (binding, functional, and neutralizing antibody, B-cell, T-cell memory, etc.)?		
7.4 Is there any previous human experience with this vaccine (safety and immunogenicity records)?		
Any evidence for or against disease enhancement?		
7.5 Describe other key information that may impact benefit-risk		
8. Adverse Event (AE) Assessment of the Vaccine Platform (*see Instructions):		
8.1 Approximately how many humans have received this vaccine to date? If variants of the vaccine, please list separately.		
8.2 Method(s) used for safety monitoring:		
o Spontaneous reports/passive surveillance		
o Diary		
o Other active surveillance		
8.3 What criteria were used for grading the AEs?		
2007 US FDA Guidance for Industry Toxicity Grading Scale for Healthy Adult and Adolescent Volunteers Enrolled in Preventive Vaccine Clinical Trials		
If no criteria were used for grading, or if other metrics were employed, please describe:		
8.4 List and provide frequency of any related or possibly related serious* AEs, as well as any severe, expected or unexpected, AEs observed: (*see Instructions):		
8.5 List and provide frequency of any serious, unexpected statistically significantly increased AE or lab abnormality in vaccinee vs. control groups:		
Describe the control group: _____.		
8.6 List and provide frequency of Adverse Events of Special Interest		
8.7 Did a Data Safety Monitoring Board (DSMB) or its equivalent oversee the study?		
Did it identify any safety issue of concern?		
If so describe:		
9. Overall Risk Assessment		
9.1 Please summarize key safety issues of concern identified to date, if any:		
how should they be addressed going forward		
9.2 What is the potential for causing serious unwanted effects and toxicities in:		
healthy humans?		
immunocompromised humans?		
human neonates, infants, children?		

pregnancy and in the fetus in humans?		
elderly?		
in any other special populations (e.g., institutionalized population, individuals with associated chronic comorbidity)?		
References		

APPENDIX V.E - Inactivated Viral Vaccines

E. Brighton Collaboration Standardized Template for Risk Assessment of Inactivated Viral Vaccine Candidates		
	Inform-ation	Comments /Concerns
1. Authorship and Affiliation		
1.1 Author(s) and affiliation (s)		
1.2 Date completed/updated		
2. Basic Vaccine information		
2.1 Vaccine name		
2.2 Virus name, genus, family, strains/serotypes, origin (e.g., geography, patient, asymptomatic), and any other specific characteristics such as genetic modifications		
2.3 Substrate for vaccine virus growth (e.g., cell substrate, eggs, animal, etc.)		
2.4 Inactivation method		
2.5 Adjuvant (if applicable)		
2.6 Final vaccine formulation components		
2.7 Route and method of delivery (e.g., intramuscular injection, microneedles, skin patch, intranasal, other mucosal)		
3. Target Pathogen and Population		
3.1 What is the target pathogen?		
3.2 What are the disease manifestations caused by the target pathogen in humans, for the following categories:		
• In healthy people		
• In immunocompromised people		
• In neonates, infants, children		
• During pregnancy and in the fetus		
• In elderly		
• In any other special populations		
3.3 Briefly, what are the key epidemiologic characteristics of the disease caused by the target pathogen (e.g., incubation period, communicable period, route/s of transmission, case fatality rate, transmissibility characteristics such as basic reproductive ratio (R_0), and spontaneous mutation)?		
3.4 What sections of the population are most affected by the target pathogen (e.g., pediatric, pregnant, lactating women (breast feeding), adult, elderly)		

3.5 What is known about the immune responses, duration, and potential correlates of protective immunity to the target pathogen or to the disease?		
3.6 Please describe any other key information about the target pathogen or population that may inform benefit-risk		
4. Characteristics of Antigen		
4.1 Virus strains, sequence (including homology among strains), source, propagation, disruption, whole virus or subunit/subvirion (if applicable)?		
4.2 Is the vaccine likely to induce immunity to all strains/genotypes of the target pathogen? What is the evidence?		
4.3 What is known about the immune response to the vaccine in animals and/or humans (binding, neutralizing antibody, functional, and, B-cell, T-cell memory, etc.)?		
5. Inactivation Method(s)		
5.1 Method/s (e.g., thermal, beta propiolactone, UV, formaldehyde, ionizing radiation) and potential impact on safety		
5.2 At what stage of the downstream process is inactivation/s performed and why?		
5.3 QC/confirmation method/log reduction in viability		
5.4 Could the inactivation method/s compromise the antigenic structure of the vaccine (e.g., conformation of the protein antigens)		
6. Adjuvant (optional, if applicable)		
6.1 Describe the type of adjuvant, if it has been tested in humans, whether novel or commercialized, and if applicable, what other vaccines (preventive and therapeutic) are formulated with this adjuvant		
6.2 What is the evidence that an adjuvant improves/boosts/enhances the immune response?		
6.3 What is the mechanism of action of the adjuvant (if known)?		
6.4 How is the adjuvant formulated with the antigen?		
6.5 How might the adjuvant impact the safety profile of the vaccine?		
6.6 Summarize the safety findings (preclinical and clinical) with the adjuvant, formulated with any antigen		
7. Delivery and Administration		
7.1 Describe how the mode of vaccine delivery may impact safety (e.g., intramuscular by needle injection, microneedles, intranasal, oral, or combination thereof)		
7.2 If the vaccine is part of a heterologous prime-boost regimen, describe the regimen that this vaccine is a part of and the possible impact on safety		
8. Toxicology and Nonclinical		
8.1 What is the possible risk of autoimmunity or a harmful immune response?		
8.2 Summarize the preclinical safety data that supports the use of this product in humans including any related information from similar products		
8.3 Summarize the preclinical immunogenicity and efficacy data that supports the use of this product in humans including any related information from similar products		

8.4 What is the evidence of disease enhancement or absence thereof <i>in vitro</i> or in animal models? ¹³		
8.5 Would the vaccine in its final formulation have any impact on innate immunity? If so, what are the implications for benefit-risk?		
9. Human Efficacy and Other Important Information		
9.1 What is the evidence that the vaccine would generate a protective immune response in humans (e.g., natural history, passive immunization, animal challenge studies)?		
9.2 Describe other key information that may impact benefit-risk		
10. Adverse Event (AE) Assessment of the Vaccine Platform (*see Instructions):		
10.1 Approximately how many humans have received this vaccine to date? If variants of the vaccine, please list separately. _____		
10.2 Method(s) used for safety monitoring:		
• Spontaneous reports/passive surveillance		
• Diary		
• Other active surveillance		
10.3 What criteria were used for grading the AEs?		
• 2007 US FDA Guidance for Industry Toxicity Grading Scale for Healthy Adult and Adolescent Volunteers Enrolled in Preventive Vaccine Clinical Trials		
• If no criteria were used for grading, or if other metrics were employed, please describe:		
10.4 List and provide frequency of any related or possibly related serious* AEs and well as any severe expected or unexpected AEs observed: (*see Instructions):		
10.5 List and provide frequency of any serious, unexpected significantly increased AE or lab abnormality in vaccinee vs. control groups:		
• Describe the control group: _____.		
10.6 List and provide frequency of Adverse Events of Special Interest		
10.7 What is the evidence of disease enhancement (if any) in humans?		
10.8 Did a Data Safety Monitoring Board (DSMB) or its equivalent oversee the study?		
• Did it identify any safety issue of concern?		
• If so describe:		
11. Overall Risk Assessment		
11.1 Please summarize key safety issues of concern identified to date, if any:		
• how should they be addressed going forward		
11.2 What is the potential for causing serious unwanted effects and toxicities in:		
• healthy humans?		
• immunocompromised humans?		
• human neonates, infants, children?		
• pregnancy and in the fetus in humans?		

• elderly?		
• in any other special populations (e.g., institutionalized populations, individuals with associated chronic comorbidity)?		
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